

ISic1332

I.Sicily inscription 1332

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Θ(εοῖς)] Κ(αταχθονίους)

2. [---]ος ἔζ[ησεν]

3. ἔτ[η]ζ μῆνε[ς---]

4. ἐπ[οίη]σεν αὐτοῦ ἡ

5. σύ[μβ]λος μνήμης

6. [χ]άρις

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

To the subterranean deities. [Name?] lived for [?] years and [?] months. Her partner built this for her memory.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492940

EDCS 39101705

PHI 140828

PHI 316246

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0511 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 155

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